

To the procedure of reference comparison (К процедуре эталонного сопоставления)

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В исследовании рассматриваются структурные и семантические особенности наречий в языке пашто в сопоставлении с русским языком с применением сравнительно-типологического метода. Теоретической основой служит концепция опорной (метаязыковой) модели, при этом теория наречий русского языка используется в качестве стандарта для анализа. В работе рассматриваются исторические и современные взгляды на статус наречия, его функции, словообразовательные модели и классификации в русской лингвистике, подчёркивается её всесторонняя и системная разработанность. Цель исследования — выявление универсальных и специфических особенностей наречий в типологически различных языках, обоснование методологической роли сравнительного анализа в лингвистических исследованиях.

ABSTRACT

The study examines the structural and semantic features of adverbs in Pashto in comparison with Russian, using the comparative-typological method. The theoretical basis relies on the concept of a reference (metalanguage) model, with Russian adverb theory serving as the standard for analysis. The work reviews historical and modern perspectives on adverb status, functions, word-formation models, and classifications in Russian linguistics, emphasizing its comprehensive and systematic coverage. The research aims to identify universal and language-specific features of adverbs in typologically distinct languages, substantiating the methodological role of comparative analysis in linguistic studies.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

сравнительно-типологический метод, метаязык, теория наречия, русский язык, язык пашто, структурные особенности, семантические особенности, словообразовательные модели, универсалии, языковая специфика.

KEYWORDS

comparative-typological method, metalanguage, adverb theory, Russian language, Pashto language, structural features, semantic features, word-formation models, universals, language specificity.

The reference comparison is based on the idea of common properties—universals—that are inherent in all languages or most languages. It formed the basis of universal grammars created in the Middle Ages and given various names in the history of science: “logical grammar” → “philosophical grammar” → “universal grammar (or, in other words, translational or speculative grammar)”. Universal grammar became the impetus for the formation of the comparative-typological method of studying languages.

Comparative-typological language study is understood as the examination of a specific language against the background of a model accepted as a reference language.

According to B.A. Uspensky, the reference language is a “metalanguage” in relation to the languages being characterized.¹ This concept was borrowed into linguistics from logic.² The prefix “meta-” is generally used to denote a language or theory whose symbols describe another language. In this case, two or more natural languages are compared in order to identify isomorphic and allomorphic features in the representation of the phenomenon under study. Metalinguistics is interpreted by scientists as a deductively derived model for constructing natural language.

In addition to metalanguage itself, comparative studies may use another natural language that is better studied in this regard as a reference point. In this regard, B.A. Uspensky writes: "A simple linguistic statement that a certain phenomenon exists in a certain language implies an implicit reference to a language or set of languages in which the same phenomenon exists. <...>, most linguistic statements about the properties of a particular language have a typological basis and imply a reference to some standard, which may vary depending on the content of the statement."³

At the same time, the theory of a certain natural language, accepted as an implied norm, can also act as a metalanguage function, which is common practice for foreign language textbook authors when the learner's native language serves as

¹ According to B.A. Uspensky, "metalanguage is opposed to object language. The author notes: "If we study, analyze, and describe a language L 1, we need language L 2 to formulate the results of our study of language L 1 or the rules for using language L 1. In this case, we call L 1 the object language and L 2 the 'metalanguage' (p. 58). The main property of a metalanguage is its invariance, i.e., its focus on modeling human language as a phenomenon and a whole, realized in specific languages as its variants. In other words, the prefix “meta-” indicates a system through comparison with which some other system is explained and described. B.A. Uspensky suggests distinguishing between two reference languages: the minimal one, which he understands as “the theoretical plural product of all characterized (in a certain aspect) languages (models), i.e., as a model invariant for all these languages,” and the maximum, which is “the theoretical-multiple sum of all the characteristics of the languages (models) being described.” See also: R. Carnap, *Introduction to semantics*. 1946 - pp. 3-4.

² Carnap R. *Logische Syntax der Sprache*. Schriften zur wiss. Weltauffassung. VIII, Wien, 1934.; Tarski A. *Introduction to the Logic and Methodology of the Deductive Sciences*. - Vienna, 1936.

³ Uspensky B. A. *Ibid.*, p. 60. See also Arakine V. D. *Comparative Typology of English and Russian Languages*. - Moscow, 2005, where it is stated that the results of such a comparison are relative and can be considered reliable only in relation to this particular case (p. 35).

the standard.⁴ In this comparison, as noted above, the first is the measuring device (it acts as the standard), and the other is the measured object. There are a number of studies conducted within this framework. In this case, the standard can be understood as a mirror or background and is interpreted in different ways.⁵, namely:

- as a measure of a certain phenomenon in one language and its application to the material of another language being studied (Choi Sun Mi, 2006. Dan Jie, 2012.);
- as one of the objects of study, when two independent languages are compared in relation to one linguistic phenomenon (Gao Xin, 2007, Slepushkina E.V., 2008, Aliyarishorehdel Mahbubeh, 2012, Ma Xiangfei, 2018, Li Wenzhu, 2019, Ma Mengfei, 2020, Nan Yanhua, 2022, etc.);
- as a factor causing interference, resulting in student errors (Kotova Yu.A., 2006);
- as a source of parallels when translating words of the target language. (Mazael O.M., 2014, Qiu Xuen, 2021, Ho Xiaojun, 2022);
- as a “double mirror” that occurs when comparing two languages, each of which is interpreted as a mirror for the other (Moazen Zadeh Zeinab, 2010).

In this thesis, the Pashto adverb is examined through the prism of the theory of the Russian adverb, which is taken as a standard.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the scientific thesis analyzes the main approaches to the structural and semantic study of adverbs as parts of speech in Russian and Pashto. It is shown that Russian linguistics has developed a multifaceted

⁴ See: Uspensky B.A. Ibid. - p. 61, where it is noted that Latin grammars created according to the Greek model (e.g., Priscian's grammar) can serve as an example of this. The author also notes that grammars of national and other languages are often compiled in this way.

⁵ Verkhoturrova K.S. Fire in the Mirror of the Russian Language: Abstract of a Candidate of Philology Dissertation. – Stavropol, 2009. – 23 p.; Marshalek L. Russian Spelling in the Mirror of Polish Orthographic Consciousness: Abstract of a Candidate of Philology Dissertation. – Veliky Novgorod, 2002. 20 p.; Magadova S.Ts. The concept of ‘human’ in the mirror of Lak phraseological units: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Makhachkala, 2017.-22 p.; Mazael O.M. Intellectual qualities of man in the mirror of Russian phraseology: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Voronezh, 2014. – 20 p.; Pinzhakova Yu.V. The form of an object in the mirror of Russian literary language: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Yekaterinburg, 2009. – 26 p.; Slepushkina E.V. Phraseology of the Russian and English languages in the mirror of national mentality: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Pyatigorsk, 2008. – 23 p.; Petkova Z.A. Russian onomatopoeic words in the mirror of Bulgarian speakers: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Moscow, 2011. – 20 p.; Choi Sun Mi. The syllabic structure of Russian word forms ‘as seen’ by Korean speakers: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Moscow, 2006. – 21 p; Gao Xin Word order in Russian as reflected in Chinese. Sciences: abstract... dissertation. Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2007. – 23 p.; Ma Mengfei. Semantics of Russian verbs with the meaning of ridicule as reflected in Chinese: abstract... dissertation. Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2020. – 27 p.; Deng Jie. Positional patterns of the Russian phonetic system in the mirror of Chinese: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2012. – 26 p.; Kotova Yu.A. The functioning of perfective and imperfective verbs in Russian: in the mirror of the Chinese language: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2006. -22 p.; Moazen Zadeh Zeynab. The category of Russian nominal locativity in the mirror of the Persian language: a pragmatic aspect: abstract... dissertation. Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2010. - 26 p.; Aliyarishorehdel Mahbubeh. Passive reflexive constructions in Russian: interaction of grammatical and semantic categories: in the mirror of the Persian language: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2012. – 26 p. Along with the concept of mirror in this sense, the concept of background can also be used.

theory of adverbs based on syntactic, morphological, and semantic features. Historical and contemporary views on the status of adverbs, their functions, word-formation models, and classifications are considered. The theory of adverbs in Russian, which has received the most complete and systematic coverage, is taken as a reference model for comparison. The methodology of comparative analysis as a tool for identifying universals and specifics in the structure and semantics of adverbs in typologically different languages is justified. Pashto adverbs will be studied based on the principles developed in Russian linguistics within the framework of comparative-typological analysis.

REFERENCES:

1. Uspensky, B. A. Language universals and current problems of typological description of language / B. A. Uspensky / Language universals and linguistic typology. – M., 1969. Carnap R. Logische Syntax der Sprache. Schriften zur wiss. Weltauffassung. VIII, Wien, 1934
2. Verkhoturova K.S. Fire in the Mirror of the Russian Language: Abstract of a Candidate of Philology Dissertation. – Stavropol, 2009. – 23 p.
3. Marshalek L. Russian Spelling in the Mirror of Polish Orthographic Consciousness: Abstract of a Candidate of Philology Dissertation. – Veliky Novgorod, 2002. 20 p.
4. Magadova S.Ts. The concept of ‘human’ in the mirror of Lak phraseological units: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences.–Makhachkala, 2017.-22 p.
5. Mazael O.M. Intellectual qualities of man in the mirror of Russian phraseology: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Voronezh, 2014. – 20 p.
6. Pinzhakova Yu.V. The form of an object in the mirror of Russian literary language: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Yekaterinburg, 2009. – 26 p.
7. Slepshkina E.V. Phraseology of the Russian and English languages in the mirror of national mentality: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Pyatigorsk, 2008. – 23 p.
8. Petkova Z.A. Russian onomatopoeic words in the mirror of Bulgarian speakers: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Moscow, 2011. – 20 p.;
9. Choi Sun Mi. The syllabic structure of Russian word forms ‘as seen’ by Korean speakers: abstract... Ph.D. thesis in philology. – Moscow, 2006. – 21 p
10. Gao Xin Word order in Russian as reflected in Chinese. Sciences: abstract... dissertation. Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2007. – 23 p.
11. Ma Mengfei. Semantics of Russian verbs with the meaning of ridicule as reflected in Chinese: abstract... dissertation. Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2020. – 27 p.

12. Deng Jie. Positional patterns of the Russian phonetic system in the mirror of Chinese: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2012. – 26 p.
13. Kotova Yu.A. The functioning of perfective and imperfective verbs in Russian: in the mirror of the Chinese language: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2006. -22 p.
14. Moazen Zadeh Zeynab. The category of Russian nominal locativity in the mirror of the Persian language: a pragmatic aspect: abstract... dissertation. Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2010. - 26 p.
15. Aliyarishorehdel Mahbubeh. Passive reflexive constructions in Russian: interaction of grammatical and semantic categories: in the mirror of the Persian language: abstract... dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Philological Sciences. – Moscow, 2012. – 26 p.